

IMPROVEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. In the article, based on the analysis of the specific features of the processes of educational relations organized in educational institutions, the correct organization and management of the processes of educational relations in general secondary educational institutions - to change the worldview of students, in them Issues such as honor, love, that is, they serve to form feelings and characteristics suitable for our national mentality, have been revealed.

Keywords: higher educational institutions, educational works, practice-oriented education, teaching methodology.

INTRODUCTION

The most effective way to educate the student community in the organization and management of educational work processes in higher education institutions is to set requirements and set a perspective based on their common interests.

The requirements will have a positive result only if they are carefully developed pedagogically:

1) Pedagogical requirements for the student should be combined with respect for each member of the team. This is an important part of pedagogical etiquette, which every group leader should not forget. More demands are placed on the best students of the group, that is, of the team, thereby giving them special trust and respect.

2) The team of pedagogues sets the requirements taking into account the specific conditions of a particular group. Every year, it is decided what requirements to impose on students in a certain quarter, semester or academic year. It is necessary to demand from students not what has been achieved, but what has been set as a task.

3) The requirements are clear and the possibilities of fulfillment are taken into account. Students should clearly understand what is required of them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is to familiarize students with the content of the requirements and monitor their importance on a regular basis. It is very important to set perspectives in educating the student body. If the team does not have an

interesting, clear goal, it is impossible to find a way to organize and consolidate it. There are two main ways to define prospects:

1. The teacher himself puts the main pedagogical requirement before the students. In doing so, he shows ways to solve these tasks and tries to interest team members;

2. Team members promote interesting activities, the team leader supports this initiative and helps to find ways to implement it. The first method is set at the initial stage of forming the student team - it is called the perspective for the near future. The second one is called future prospects, which are set by group activists at a much higher level. If all the members of the team put the set prospects, it is called long-term prospects and means that the team has been formed. As the student body grows and strengthens, medium and long-term prospects are set before the team. For example: making toys for the adopted kindergarten, holding a harvest festival, organizing a summer trip around the beloved country, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order for the team to always move forward in its activities, it is necessary to put new, interesting perspectives in front of it. If the community life is not vibrant, then it will be very difficult to restore these ties. Traditions play an important role in the formation of the student community. Nothing can strengthen the team traditionally. Creating traditions and preserving them is an important task of education. A school without traditions cannot be a good school. Existing traditions can be conditionally divided into two groups [1]:

- A) daily life traditions,
- B) holiday traditions.

Daily life traditions include educational activities of students, various types of mutual assistance, work activities - taking care of young fruit seedlings, feeding animals, helping elderly people living alone, and other chores. Holiday traditions include Nowruz, Independence Day, graduation party,

"Literacy holidays" are included. In any case, the holidays should be bright, fun, cheerful, festive. The main goal is that the students understand the moral content of the event, and only if they have a conscious attitude, then its effect will be strong. During the stages of development of the team, in the process of various activities of team members, unique traditions arise in each HEI. These new traditions will be connected with the educational activities carried out in this higher educational institution, will enliven and decorate its life. Therefore, students are given great opportunities to actively participate in the origin of the

new tradition. Teachers should not impose this or that extra tradition on the student body. Their task is to explain to team members the need to create traditions, to work together in preparing and carrying out traditions, and to teach students to continue these traditions, without making them feel or breaking their initiative. It is always necessary to introduce innovations that reflect new pedagogical requirements and increase its educational value. Traditions increase from year to year and gradually establish the uniqueness of HEI. Thus, perspectives and traditions related to learning activities are important at all levels of community development.

Based on the above, it is possible to indicate the following as the main factors of educating young people in a team spirit:

- to give examples from the work experience of the most advanced enterprise teams, from the lives of families and parents who are exemplary in unity, unity, mutual support as a team and comrades;

- to explain, on the basis of comprehensive examples, how people should be a community in their lives, live in a friendly brotherly relationship with each other, work and create, and open a great way for their lives and marriages to always be beautiful and happy. On the contrary, if people live their lives without properly evaluating the community and its requirements, it is expected that marriage will pass without heart, joy and spiritual wealth. Philosophically and pedagogically, he interprets these characteristics and principles of the community in a wide and deep way. Community and individual relationships are important. A person's personality is related to his relations with other people, society, homeland, and all opportunities. So, a person is a biological concept, a personal social concept. In the example of the Shura society, we can see that people's natural needs are condemned and turned into social mechanisms, nature is also politicized, and people are devalued by ideological oppression. The general interest of the team and the personal interest of the students are combined and harmonized. And in this case, students learn that the goal and interest of the team is more important than personal interest, that one person thinks about everyone (everyone in his team), and everyone (the whole team) thinks about every person in this team, care understanding the need to do will increase students' consciousness. More importantly, the mutual respect of team members turns into friendship. Now the teenager realizes that life without friends is very boring and meaningless. Therefore, it is appropriate for the leader of each group to explain to his students what ways and means can be used to form a team, and its essence. It is important to educate students in the

spirit of community based on the use of aphorisms about community and comradely mutual aid, reading books, giving examples from events, holding events. Students can effectively fight for its implementation only if they thoroughly understand the nature of the community.

The problem of the community and the individual is considered one of the most urgent theoretical and practical issues of educating the young generation. From this point of view, it is the task of general secondary education institutions to accustom students to public spirit, community life, to organize as a team, to create skills, and to form public consciousness. A person should not only be fully developed, but he should be socially active, use all his strength and capabilities to serve the Motherland, and find his place in society. In addition, a person's personal capabilities, skills and abilities are effectively used in serving the Motherland. One of the main features of the community is the formation of patriotism in students. Because the feeling of patriotism is caring for one's motherland and destiny. A true patriot fights for his motherland, prosperity and freedom of his people.

Students learn about mutual assistance between people, communities, and countries and understand their meaning. It is an excellent resource for educating people, students, in reading letters and in mutual relations, the feeling of sharing and helping. In addition, the next form of peer support is the permanent attachment of students who are good learners to students who are not learning. Likewise, attaching to a group, group, etc. Another form of peer support can be seen in preparing lessons as a small group. Friendly mutual support of students is seen in art lovers, preparing students for sports competitions, helping them in the work of leaders. Friendly mutual support is a way to actively participate students in Saturday and Sunday classes.

CONCLUSION

We pay special attention to the appreciation of any kind of work in teaching students to work and having the right attitude towards work. Hashar has its historical and social roots. In the past, as a result of hard labor, poor farmers were alone and did not have the opportunity to work the land allotted to them. Hashar in its essence is team work, and it can be called team work dedicated by the team for the benefit of a certain person. Because in this way, a certain person, on the one hand, will benefit materially, and on the other hand, he will be enriched spiritually.

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